

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

IMPLEMENTATION OF IMPROVED INDICATORS ON BIODIVERSITY LOSS

Deliverable 6.3

Summary

Work Package	6
Deliverable N°	6.3
Dissemination Level	Public
Type	R-document, report
Lead Partner	Universitat Politècnica de València
Due Date	30 th August
Submission Date	
Status	Final
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About CLEVER

Project Number	101060765
Project Title	CLEVER: Creating leverage to enhance biodiversity outcomes of global biomass trade
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-15
Start date	1 st September 2022
End date	31 st August 2025
Coordinator	RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAT BONN

This document has been prepared in the framework of the project CLEVER. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the European Research Executive Agency under HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions, grant agreement n°101060765; and from the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10038491]

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0. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Agriculture is linked to multiple environmental impacts, among others land use change (LUC), greenhouse gas emissions, and freshwater eutrophication, which, in turn, are drivers of biodiversity loss. Increasing agri-food exports and trade in agricultural commodities cause the displacement of these impacts along global and increasingly interlinked supply chains, with the associated environmental footprints. Given the complexity and scale of the impacts on biodiversity and the underlying drivers, the quantification of biodiversity impacts from human interventions and future policies requires capturing the causal relationships between LUC, environmental pollution, and the ultimate effects on biodiversity. This can benefit from applying forward-looking, dynamic approaches combined with spatially-explicit data on land uses and species and habitat distribution. This deliverable aims to develop indicators of biodiversity loss based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approaches and to integrate them into the Global Biosphere Management Model (GLOBIOM) for the subsequent analysis of environmental footprints and future biodiversity impacts from policy interventions. Specifically, a dedicated case study on Brazilian soy supply chains arriving in the EU from 2004 to 2020 has been developed. This included the development of a new set of characterisation factors (CFs) for biodiversity loss due to land transformation and land occupation (i.e., land stress) in South America and Africa, respectively, based on CLEVER D2.4. CFs derived from existing impact assessment methods in LCA, namely LC-IMPACT, have been linked to crucial model variables in GLOBIOM and the above-mentioned new set of CFs for land stress obtained in this deliverable. In addition, long-term projections of global LUC and biodiversity impacts from agricultural and forest activities have been derived with the extended GLOBIOM model considering land dynamics in the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) framework.

The case study results on the biodiversity footprint of Brazilian soy supply chains highlight land stress (transformation and occupation) as the primary driver of biodiversity loss. The intense deforestation induced by soy crops is reflected in the greater impact scores for the municipalities located in states such as Rio Grande do Sul and Maranhão. The analysis of the biodiversity impact of the agriculture and forestry sector for 2020 and future scenarios in GLOBIOM revealed that globally, land stress is the primary driver of impacts on terrestrial ecosystems, while water stress dominates the impacts on aquatic ecosystems. The study also shows significant variations in impacts across regions and even within countries, with a more contrasted ranking of pressures.

1. INTRODUCTION

Through centuries, human activities have contributed to the constant decline in biodiversity (Ceballos et al., 2015; Johnson et al., 2017). Yet current extinction rates are exceptionally high, about 1000 times the background rate of extinction (Pimm et al., 2014). At least 25% of species are currently threatened, with around 1 million species facing extinction unless action is taken to reduce the intensity of drivers of biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2019). Direct drivers of biodiversity loss include land use and land use change (LUC), climate change, pollution, invasive alien species, and the anthropogenic exploitation of wildlife (IPBES, 2019). Land use is the main direct driver of terrestrial biodiversity loss because it contributes to habitat degradation, fragmentation, and overall reduction (Tilman et al., 2017). Climate change also exacerbates the terrestrial biodiversity decline (between 0.92% to 5.1% per decade) (Pereira et al., 2024); while biodiversity loss causes ecosystem degradation (Hooper et al., 2012), reducing the carbon storage potential of natural land and contributing to climate change (Weiskopf et al., 2024). Many studies emphasise the need for combined initiatives and policies to halt biodiversity loss and effectively progress towards conservation and broader sustainability goals (Leclère et al., 2020; Tilman et al., 2017). Adopted in 2022, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) sets 20 targets to be met in 2030, aiming to halt and reverse biodiversity loss by that year. Specifically, targets 7 and 8 refer to mitigating the impacts of environmental pollution and climate change on biodiversity.

As a land-use and emission-intensive activity, agriculture is linked to multiple environmental impacts, including greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, water scarcity, freshwater eutrophication, soil acidification, LUC, and biodiversity loss (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2015; Zabel et al., 2019). At the same time, increasing agri-food exports and trade in agricultural commodities cause the displacement of these impacts along increasingly global supply chains, with the associated environmental footprints. Several studies combine trade data (Chaudhary et al., 2016, 2017; Chaudhary & Kastner, 2016) or multi-regional input-output (MRIO) databases with quantitative indicators to measure the potential species lost or threatened due to the consumption of agricultural products based on the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Boakes et al., 2024; Irwin et al., 2022; Lenzen et al., 2012; Sun et al., 2022). Not surprisingly, agricultural commodities produced in the tropics, where large-scale commodity-driven deforestation occurs, are associated with higher impacts on species richness, e.g., coffee, soybean, cocoa, and oil palm (Oakley & Bicknell, 2022). Thus, the countries that are leading importers and consumers of these commodities have the largest footprints, e.g., Australia, the United States, EU countries, China, etc. (Chaudhary & Kastner, 2016).

Most of the studies mentioned above focus on the impacts on species richness derived from changes in land uses based on species-area relationship (SAR) models. These predict regional and global biodiversity loss due to land use (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2018). For instance, the matrix SAR (Koh & Ghazoul, 2010) aims to quantify species richness considering habitat heterogeneity. The countryside SAR also reflects how species adapt to human-modified habitats, crucial to measuring land-use-driven biodiversity impacts (Pereira et al., 2014). Based on observed land use distribution, the countryside SAR predicts the final equilibrium level of species extinctions per ecoregion, taking levels prior to human intervention as a baseline. However, it does not inform on the timing of extinctions (Chaudhary & Kastner, 2016). Chaudhary et al. (2015) and Chaudhary & Brooks (2018) use the countryside SAR to quantify regional and global species loss due to land occupation and transformation for five taxa (mammals, birds, amphibians, reptiles

and plants) in 804 terrestrial ecoregions, considering relative species affinity to different land uses and intensity levels. The resulting characterisation factors (CFs) provide potential species loss across the five taxa per unit area (m^2) for five broad land use types (forestry, plantations, cropland, pastureland, and urban) under three management intensity levels (minimal, light, and intense use). Several harmonisation initiatives recommend using these CFs to estimate biodiversity impacts from land use (FAO, 2020; UNEP, 2017). These CFs have been commonly used in life cycle assessment (LCA) studies (Crenna et al., 2019; Gaudreault et al., 2020; Lucas et al., 2021, 2023). Crenna et al. (2019) include the biodiversity effects of other impacts of agricultural production by using the endpoint indicator “ecosystems quality” from the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) method Recipe 2016 (Huijbregts et al., 2017). This reflects the Potentially Disappeared Fraction (PDF) of species over time due to ecosystem damage. The LCIA method LC Impact (Verones et al., 2020) also implements the global PDF as a good indicator of the risk of extinction, that is, of the fraction of species committed to global extinction.

A few biodiversity indicators aim to reflect a broad-sense biodiversity state beyond species richness in a particular taxon. The Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII) (Scholes & Biggs, 2005) estimates how the average abundance of the native terrestrial species in a region compares with their abundances in the absence of pronounced human impacts (De Palma et al., 2021). The mean species abundance (MSA) indicator in the GLOBIO3 model (Alkemade et al., 2009) quantifies the mean abundance of original species relative to their abundance in undisturbed ecosystems, considering several drivers (LUC, land use intensity, fragmentation, climate change, atmospheric nitrogen deposition, and infrastructure development). The Living Planet Index (LPI) (Loh et al., 2005) measures the average decline in monitored wildlife populations, although its limitation to be interpreted as a change in abundance has been discussed (Puurtinen et al., 2022). The Terrestrial Area of Habitat (AOH) (Brooks et al., 2019) captures the habitat available to a species within its range. It has been used to monitor habitat loss and fragmentation and also to produce global maps of the species richness and threatened species of mammals and birds (Lumbierres et al., 2022). Oliveira et al. (2019) developed an integrated biodiversity relevance index for Brazil based on a spatial model that includes information on phylogenetic diversity, species richness, endemism, and composition. The Species Threat Abatement and Restoration (STAR) metric (Mair et al., 2021) quantifies the potential benefit for threatened species of actions to reduce threats and restore habitat. Irwin et al. (2022) introduce the non-normalised STAR (nSTAR) metric, which has no units and provides an additive measure of extinction risk, facilitating the link with MRIO databases. Boakes et al. (2024) develop CFs for species richness (species $\times km^2$) and rarity-weighted richness (range fractions $\times km^2$) driven by both land use and GHG emissions. The latter considers the Global Temperature Change Potential (GTP) of food-related GHG emissions and the sensitivity of biodiversity to climate change under the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP). The rarity-weighted species richness indicator measures local biodiversity loss relative to an unimpacted baseline.

All of these indicators illustrate that to comprehensively assess the issue of biodiversity loss, it is recommended to combine several indicators, ideally addressing the multiple facets of biodiversity beyond species richness, to provide complementary perspectives on the issue of biodiversity loss. Furthermore, the choice of framework is critical in

determining the results of the biodiversity footprint. Given the complexity and scale of the impacts on biodiversity and the underlying drivers, the quantification of biodiversity impacts from human interventions and future policies requires capturing the causal relationships between LUC, environmental pollution, and the ultimate effects on habitats and species (Crenna et al., 2020; Marques et al., 2021). This can benefit from applying forward-looking, dynamic approaches (Leclère et al., 2020; Newbold et al., 2015) combined with spatially explicit data on land uses and species and habitat distribution.

1. OBJECTIVES

CLEVER investigates how international trade in agricultural and forest products drives biodiversity impacts through non-food biomass supply chains and what are the main biodiversity loss hotspots in major producing and exporting countries. The final goal is to develop solutions for more sustainable production and consumption of agricultural and forestry commodities to support decision-making in collaboration with policy stakeholders, the private sector, and civil society.

This deliverable (D6.3) aims to develop indicators of biodiversity loss based on LCA approaches and to integrate them into the global modelling framework GLOBIOM for the subsequent analysis of environmental footprints and future biodiversity impacts from policy interventions. Specifically, D6.3 fulfils the following objectives:

1. To estimate regionalised indicators for biodiversity loss driven by land stress and agricultural production based on available LCA impact assessment methods combined with outcomes from WP2 (D2.4) of Brazilian soybeans arriving in the European Union (EU).
2. To quantify biodiversity footprints of the commodity of interest by considering both land-use-driven and pollution-driven biodiversity loss, using fine-scale data on global imports and exports, agricultural expansion, and LUC over time.
3. To link the indicators from 1) and those from available impact assessment methods in LCA to key variables in GLOBIOM by considering the global distribution of land uses and the spatial heterogeneity and diversity in land management and agricultural practices.
4. To derive long-term projections of global LUC and biodiversity impacts from agricultural and forest activities with the extended GLOBIOM model from 3), considering land dynamics in the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) framework.

With this, D6.3 contributes to the following general objective of the project:

- Objective I: Improve our understanding of how biomass trade is linked to biodiversity outcomes and co-benefits in exporting and importing regions.

3. METHODS

3.1. Estimation of biodiversity footprints of Brazilian soy supply chains

This study applies an attributional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach (ISO, 2006a, 2006b, 2017). Following an accounting decision context (EC-JRC, 2010), the impact on biodiversity of the most critical activities along a key global supply chain is assessed, namely soy from Brazil

arriving in the EU. Brazilian soy was chosen due to its significant contribution to global trade and its potential impact on biodiversity.

The impact on biodiversity is expressed per mass of commodity traded using two units, which help to compare the biodiversity performance of the supply chains assessed. The first unit refers to the total quantity traded per supply chain from the origin (Brazil) to the EU. The second unit, known as the 'marginal unit of traded commodity', is the additional impact caused by the last unit of commodity traded. In the case of soy exports, the impacts are expressed per kg of soy-eq, defined as the quantity of raw soybeans embedded in the flows of oil, cake, and beans that ultimately arrive at the importing country at the end of each supply chain. This is the unit commonly used by the database Trase (Lathuillière et al., 2022) to quantify flows of soy and derivatives across the world. The mass of soy-eq. results from the allocation of soybeans among derivatives (oil and meal) based on data on individual shipments leaving Brazilian ports, soy production in the corresponding municipalities, and the subsequent crushing and storage facilities.

Under an attributional LCA approach, the environmental assessment consists of transforming the activity data in terms of environmental impact through CFs, assuming that the impact is a linear function of the activity data where the CFs work as the coefficient of the function (Eq. 1):

$$\text{Impact indicator} = \text{CF} \cdot \text{activity_data} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Based on data from the literature, this study covers the pressures on biodiversity related to direct land use, consumption of resources, and emissions that occur along the supply chain.

3.1.1. System description

The assessed Brazilian soy supply chains comprise a supply node referring to the jurisdiction where the soy commodities are produced in Brazil at the municipality level, an intermediate node referring to the ports of origin in Brazil, and a demand node in the destination ports in the EU. Each supply chain is the unit of analysis that helps to understand the impact on the biodiversity of the soy commodities trade from Brazil to the EU. *Trase* platform (*Trase, 2024*) provides the information used to differentiate each supply chain. *Trase* is based on Spatially Explicit Information on Production to Consumption Systems (SEI-PCS) models (Lathuillière et al., 2022), and it tracks supply chains of biomass-based commodities at subnational scales.

Figure 1. The system analysed Brazilian soy commodities marketed to the European Union.

For each supply chain, the links considered are soybean farming, processing of the soybean commodities, their domestic transportation from the producer municipality to the exporting port, and transoceanic transit from the exporting port to the destination port in the EU (Figure 1). Concerning the farming stage, two relevant impact sources of biodiversity loss are distinguished. The first is direct land-use-driven biodiversity loss due to the area used for soy cropping and the emissions associated with changes in the carbon stocks. The second source of impact corresponds to farming practices, which include soil preparation, sowing, fertilisation, and pest treatment. In addition, machinery use (transversal to the previous activities) and on-field emissions due to soil preparation and fertilisation have been considered separately to facilitate the contribution assessment. Soybean processing refers to crushing to obtain soy meal and oil in relative proportions of 80% and 19%, respectively, accounting for losses (Escobar et al., 2020). This study's geographical and temporal scope covered 2059 soy-producing municipalities in Brazil that exported soybeans or derivatives (meal and oil) to 23 EU countries from 2004 to 2020.

3.1.2. Biodiversity loss due to land occupation and land transformation: characterisation factors for soy production in Brazil at the Municipality level

The changes in the habitat driven by land use for anthropogenic purposes have been identified as the main pressure on biodiversity (Winter et al., 2017). To date, impact assessment methods quantifying the impacts of land use differentiate two types of land stress: land transformation and land occupation (Lindner et al., 2019). Land transformation is the change from a reference situation to another quality status at one specific time; it considers the modification of native landscapes induced by deforestation assigned to the analysed human activity (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2018; IPCC, 2019b). Occupation refers to continuing the (typically lower) quality status over time. The quality change can either be temporary if it is reversible or permanent if it is (partly or entirely) irreversible. Land occupation is associated with the land that, previously to the analysed use, flaunts a human-induced activity.

LCA methodology quantifies biodiversity loss by multiplying the surface area of land transformed and land occupied by their respective CFs. In this study, the CFs used for biodiversity impacts correspond to two different approaches. The first one is the method of Scherer et al. (2023), who propose global CFs for land occupation and land transformation. It is the most updated approach for estimating species richness (SR) based on Species Affinity Relationships (SAR). The second approach was developed in CLEVER D2.4. It is based on the biodiversity indicators estimated by Oliveira & Pacheco (2024) and, as an alternative to SAR, estimates species richness through the Optimising Combined Evidence in Unique Biota-OCEUB model to mitigate the sampling bias, a well-known limitation of currently available biodiversity data (Oliveira et al., 2019; 2024). Both approaches provide land occupation and transformation CFs for terrestrial biodiversity loss at the ecoregion level for different land use types and three intensities.

The methods for assessing land use-driven biodiversity loss require categorising the land used in soy farming as land occupation or transformation. In this study, land transformation corresponds to primary forest and non-forest natural formation categories of Table 1. In contrast, land occupation corresponds to the farming land category (Table 1). To estimate the impacts of soy production in Brazil due to land transformation and occupation, the CFs at the

ecoregion level of the two approaches mentioned in Section 3.1.2 are adapted to the municipality level by allocating the land occupation and land transformation calculated at a high-resolution level in each jurisdiction. In this way, an aggregated CF representative of the soy crop in each municipality is obtained (Eq. 2), which can also be considered an indicator of biodiversity loss in the municipality. Subsequently, the integrated indicator is multiplied by the soy crop area assigned to each supply chain to account for the biodiversity loss.

$$CF_{agg,m} = \frac{\sum_e^n [(CF_{occ,e} \cdot A_{occ,m} \cdot T_{occ} + CF_{tr,e} \cdot A_{tr,m}) \frac{A_{e,m}}{A_m}]}{A_{total}} \cdot 10000 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where: $CF_{agg,m}$ is the aggregated CF representative of the soy crop in each municipality m , expressed as PDF· ha⁻¹ soy crop; CF_{occ} is the CF for cropland occupation in the ecoregion where municipality m is located, as PDF· m⁻²; CF_{tr} is the CF for non-human induced land use transformed to cropland in the ecoregion where municipality m is located, PDF·m⁻²·yr⁻¹; $A_{occ,m}$ is the soy crop area occupied in the municipality m , which the immediate previous use has been human-induced, ha⁻¹; T_{occ} is the fraction of the year in which soy crops occupy the land surface; $A_{tr,m}$ corresponds to the soy crop area employed in the municipality m , for which the immediate previous use has been non-human-induced, ha⁻¹; $A_{e,m}$ is the area of the intersection between ecoregion e and municipality m , km²; A_m is the area of the municipality m , km²; and A_{total} is the total soy harvested area planted in the municipality m , ha⁻¹.

A_{occ} , A_{tr} and A_{total} were obtained as the sum of the surface area of the cells included in each land use category according to the procedure presented below to categorise the land used in the farming stage as occupied or transformed. The land cover and land use maps of MapBiomass Collection 8 (MapBiomass, 2023) are used as a basis to estimate these areas. This collection consists of yearly GeoTiff layers from 1985 to 2022, with a resolution of 30 m, where the land covered in Brazil is classified (Table 1). The A_{occ} , A_{tr} of the cells is calculated with the “area” function of the “raster” package in R (Hijmans, 2023); it differs in each cell since the layers are located in a geographic coordinate system.

Table 1: Land cover categories for Brazil

MAPBIOMASS ¹		Terrestrial habitats ²	Ecological zones ³
Level	Sublevel	Sublevel	Level
1. Primary forest	1.1. Forest Formation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperate continental - Subtropical/tropical dry - Subtropical/tropical moist lowland - Subtropical/tropical moist montane 	- Differentiate between tropical and subtropical
	1.2. Savanna Formation		
	1.3. Mangrove		
	1.4. Floodable Forest (beta)		
	1.5. Wooded Sandbank Vegetation		
2. Non-Forest Natural Formation	2.1. Wetland		
	2.2. Grassland		
	2.3. Hypersaline Tidal Flat		
	2.4. Rocky Outcrop		
	2.5. Herbaceous Sandbank Vegetation		
	2.6. Other non-Forest Formations		
3. Farming	3.1. Pasture		
	3.2. Agriculture		
	3.2.1. Temporary crop		
	3.2.1.1. Soybean		
	3.2.1.2. Sugar cane		
	3.2.1.3. Rice		
	3.2.1.4. Cotton (beta)		
	3.2.1.5. Other Temporary Crops		
	3.2.2. Perennial crop		
	3.2.2.1. Coffee		
	3.2.2.2. Citrus		
	3.2.2.3. Palm Oil (beta)		
	3.2.2.4. Other Perennial Crops		
3.3. Forest Plantation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperate continental - Subtropical/tropical dry - Subtropical/tropical moist lowland - Subtropical/tropical moist montane 		
3.4. Mosaic of Uses			
4. Non-vegetated area	4.1. Beach, Dune and Sand Spot		
	4.2. Urban Area		
	4.3. Mining		
	4.4. Other non-Vegetated Areas		
5. Water	5.1. River, Lake and Ocean		
	5.2. Aquaculture		

¹(MapBiomass, 2023), ²(Jung et al., 2020), ³(IPCC, 2006a)

3.1.3. Biodiversity loss due to emissions from changes in biomass and carbon stocks

LU and LUC induce changes in existing land uses and associated carbon stocks (above and below-ground biomass, litter, dead wood and soil), releasing emissions into the air that ultimately affect the existing biomass. LUC is linked to a specific crop, such as soy, and translates into GHG emissions when carbon stocks are lost as a one-time effect, relative to previous uses.

As a basis to estimate the emissions from LUC, the previous land cover in the soy crop areas in the analysed period is calculated following the method described in section 3.2.1. In addition, following the Tier 1 methods of the IPCC Volume 4 Chapter 5 (IPCC, 2006b; IPCC, 2019a), it was assumed that all the biomass deforested is burnt; thus, emissions from burning (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and NO_x) have also been estimated at the municipality level. It must be noted that to identify the land cover before the change to soy crops, the three previous years (yr⁻³) are considered since a common practice in the country consists of leaving a 3-year gap between the period of deforestation and the first soy season (Escobar et al., 2020). The biomass content in a specific area varies depending on the kind of cover and the spatial location. This variability was modelled using the classification of maps referred to terrestrial habitats (Jung et al., 2020) and ecological zones (IPCC, 2006, cap3) and using the biomass content available in Tables 4.7 and 4.8 of the IPCC (IPCC, 2019b).

For estimating soil carbon loss induced by soy farming, layers of soil C stocks (kg C·ha⁻¹) overlapped between the cells covered with soy crops in the analysed year and the prior cover of the land used. Soil C stock layers have the same spatial resolution as the land cover ones (30 x 30 m). They correspond to the first version of soil carbon stock maps for Brazil of MapBiomass (MapBiomass, 2024) and represent the organic carbon stocks in the top 30 cm of soil. CO₂ emissions due to changes in the C content in the soil are estimated for each cell using Eq. 3, which are summed up to obtain the total emissions (kg CO₂·ha⁻¹) in each municipality. Similar to the emissions related to biomass, CO₂ emissions due to changes in the C soil stocks are classified as LU or LUC according to the cover cleared.

$$CO_{2,m,i} = \frac{(C_{Soil_{m,i,yr-3}} - C_{Soil_{m,i,yr}})}{T} \cdot \frac{44}{12} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where $CO_{2,m,i}$ is the CO₂ emitted (kg CO₂·ha⁻¹) in the cell i representative of municipality m ; $C_{Soil_{m,i}}$ is the soil carbon stock in the cell i covered with soy crops during the analysed year (yr) and prior three years (yr⁻³) in the municipality m ; T is the number of years for which a change in the soil carbon stock is distributed, being $T = 3$ when the prior cover is in some temporary crop; otherwise, $T = 1$, assigning the carbon stock change to the first soy harvest after the LUC.

The estimated emissions are then multiplied by a CF to estimate biodiversity loss. Specifically, the endpoint CFs of LC-IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020) are used (PDF·yr·kg emission⁻¹).

3.1.4. Biodiversity loss due to pollution associated with upstream supply chain emissions

The multiple processes involved in the supply chains of study (upstream the soy-eq arrive in the EU), such as farming, processing or transport, imply resource use and pollutant emissions that ultimately affect ecosystem quality, causing biodiversity loss. This biodiversity loss has been assessed with LC-IMPACT using SimaPro software v9.3 to obtain the unit impact associated with activity data. LC-IMPACT distinguishes the environmental mechanisms (climate change, ozone

formation, acidification, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, terrestrial ecotoxicity and water stress) that affect biodiversity.

To estimate the activity data to represent the soy supply chains, input consumption for the soy farming and processing stages was obtained from the literature on LCA of soy products in various Brazilian states (see S4 in SM). It is worth noting that all the LCAs of Brazilian soy analyse rainfed farms with no-tillage practices. Farming management is as an activity variable per Brazilian state. Whenever possible, activity data representative of soy farming in the federal state where the producing municipality is located have been assigned to define the supply chains. Otherwise, the average activity data for the region (i.e., North, North-East, Centre-West, South-East, and South) is assigned. Regarding processing, activity data representative of national average values is assigned to each supply chain. S4 in SM details the raw data used to estimate input consumption in the farming and processing stages.

Fertilisation and limestone application release CO₂ and N₂O emissions, estimated by applying IPCC's Tier 1 factor emissions (IPCC, 2019d). To estimate NH₃ and NO_x emissions, the Tier 1 emission factors of the European Environmental Agency (EMEP/EEA, 2019) are applied. Nitrate leaching and phosphorus emissions have not been estimated due to the low mobility of phosphorus and the negative nitrogen and phosphorus balances in Brazilian soils (FAO, 2004; Lucas et al., 2023). In addition, on-field emissions from pesticide application are not considered because most pesticides are unspecified in the literature reviewed.

Concerning the transport processes, time-distance algorithms have been applied to estimate both domestic and transoceanic transport distances. In particular, ORS tool is used to estimate the distance between the supply and intermediate nodes based on realistic routes travelled by vehicles transporting heavy goods. The distance between the intermediate and demand nodes is calculated through the Least Cost Path, where the paths are configured, avoiding passage through land areas. Both ORS tool and Least Cost Path were run through QGIS software, v3.34.0-Prizren (QGIS, 2024).

3.2. Linking LCA impact assessment methods to GLOBIOM

3.2.1 General methodological choices

In order to calculate the impact of the land activities modelled in GLOBIOM on freshwater and terrestrial ecosystem quality in terms of potential loss of species (PDF), LC-IMPACT endpoint CFs have been implemented in GLOBIOM. These CFs can be linked to different pressures related to GLOBIOM agricultural and forestry activities: climate change, land use, freshwater eutrophication, and water stress. Additional impact drivers on biodiversity are available in LC-IMPACT (i.e., photochemical ozone formation, terrestrial acidification, freshwater and terrestrial ecotoxicity, marine eutrophication) but could not be linked to GLOBIOM in this first instance, because the related environmental flows are not covered in the model. The use of endpoint CFs for ecosystem quality, such as those from LC-IMPACT, which quantifies PDF per unit of elementary flow instead of coefficients that estimate impact per ton of product, ensures consistency with GLOBIOM's modelling framework. This alignment allows for a more accurate estimation of impacts while accounting for the model's dynamic linkages between productivity,

input use, and environmental flows. This ensures that scenario-specific assumptions and endogenous modelling of changes in production technologies within GLOBIOM are effectively captured and accurately represented in the environmental impact assessments.

Endpoint CFs from LC-IMPACT for climate change and water stress pressures have been linked respectively to agricultural GHG emissions and to water used for irrigation. Using the water for irrigation is likely to be an overestimation, as LC-IMPACT CFs quantify the impact of water consumption and not withdrawn. Regarding freshwater eutrophication, LC-IMPACT CFs are linked to the phosphorus fertiliser and manure applications calculated in GLOBIOM. As to the land use pressure, LC-IMPACT CFs and the new spatially-explicit CFs developed for South America and South Africa using outputs from CLEVER D2.4 (hereinafter called D2.4 CFs) and described in section 3.1.2 are used. For better comparability with LC-IMPACT, CFs for global-PDF are used.

GLOBIOM's environmental flow outputs to be linked to the different CFs are available at the level of 2 x 2-degree cells (LUID) intersected by country boundaries (hereinafter: LUID x Country unit) and by three agro-ecological zones: arid, humid, temperate and tropical highlands. To link the different CFs to GLOBIOM, these have first been calculated at the appropriate LUID x Country unit, by taking into consideration the level of the pressure in each LUID x Country unit. Table 2 displays the data used to compute the CFs at the right resolution.

Table 2: Data used for the harmonization between characterisation factors and land uses in GLOBIOM.

Impact assessment method	Impact driver	Spatial granularity of CF	Harmonisation needed for GLOBIOM
LC-IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020)	Climate change	World	Not applicable
	Land stress	Ecoregions	based on share of ecoregion area in LUID
	Water stress	0.05° by 0.05°	based on share of water use in LUID (CWATM data)
	Freshwater Eutrophication	Freshwater ecoregions (FEOW)	based on share of FEOW Fertiliser and manure application in LUID (Potter et al., 2012)
D2.4 (Oliveira et al., 2019, 2024)	Land stress	Ecoregions	based on share of ecoregion area in LUID

In LC-IMPACT, marginal and average endpoint CFs are available. The former is typically used in LCA to quantify the effects of relatively small, additional LUC, whereas average CFs are applied to evaluate the total impacts of land use across a specific region. Within GLOBIOM, average CFs are used as the purpose is to calculate the total impacts of a region, while marginal CFs are usually applied in the case of a product life cycle (Scherer et al., 2023). In the case of water stress, only marginal CFs are available in LC-IMPACT. For climate change and land transformation impacts, a 100 year time horizon is considered. D2.4 CFs for land occupation are average CFs,

and land transformation CFs consider a 100-year time horizon. For climate change impacts, CFs for *all effects* are used to calculate the impact on freshwater ecosystems as well; however, the level of robustness could be lower since the CFs only account for fish species. Similarly, water stress CFs for *all effects* were used because the irrigation data from GLOBIOM includes groundwater as well as surface water, but the robustness of those CFs is also lower (Verones et al., 2020). Table 3 below summarizes the methodological choices regarding the integration of the CFs in GLOBIOM.

Table 3: Methodological choices for the integration of LCA derived CFs in GLOBIOM. In the formulas EF: Environmental flow; CF: Characterisation factors; LU: Land use type; LU_{from}: Land use type before transformation; LU_{to}: land use after transformation.

	ENVIRONMENTAL FLOW EF		CHARACTERISATION FACTORS CF					IMPACT	
	GLOBIOM Variable	Unit	Method	Damage on	Marginal/ avg	Impact considered	Unit	Formula	Unit
CLIMATE CHANGE	GHG emissions	CO2eq/year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater and terrestrial	Average	All effects, 100y	PDF./kg	EF x CF	PDF./year
LAND OCCUPATION	Land area per land use type	ha/year	LC-IMPACT D2.4	terrestrial	Average	na	PDF/(m ² .y)	$\sum_{LU} 1y * EF_{LU} * CF_{LU}$	PDF./year
LAND TRANSFORMATION	Land conversions between land use types	ha/year	LC-IMPACT D2.4	terrestrial	Average	100y	PDF./ha	$\sum_{LU_{from,to}} EF_{LU_{from,to}} * (CF_{LU_{to}} - CF_{LU_{from}})$	PDF./year
WATER CONSUMPTION	irrigation	km ³ /year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater	Marginal	All effects	PDF./m ³	EF x CF	PDF./year
FRESHWATER EUTROPHICATION	P inputs	tonnes P/year	LC-IMPACT	Freshwater	Average	Certain	PDF./kg	EF x CF	PDF./year

3.2.2. Land stress

To enable the linkage of the land use CFs with GLOBIOM land use information, the land use categories of GLOBIOM are linked to the land use categories of LC-IMPACT and D2.4 CFs (see Table 4). For LC-IMPACT land uses, the total cropland area is split between permanent and annual crops, considering that palm oil, sugar cane and plantation forests are *permanent crops*, and the rest are *annual crops*. Due to the lack of more explicit management intensity information in GLOBIOM, the area of *Managed forest* is equally distributed into *Extensive* and *Intensive Forest*. Since D2.4 CFs are not specific for *annual vs permanent croplands*, or for *extensive vs intensive forest*, but for *Croplands* and *Managed Forests*, the class is further divided into intensity levels: *minimal*, *light* and *intense*. To align the land use classes with the existing GLOBIOM land use categories, the average value of the CFs for the different intensities is used. These approximations, however, reduce the precision in assessing the impacts of land intensification and will need refinement in future stages.

Table 4: Land use classes in LCA impact assessment methods and mapping to GLOBIOM land use classes

Method	Land use classes	Mapping to GLOBIOM
LC-IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020)	Annual cropland, Permanent Cropland, Pasture, Urban, Extensive Forest, Intensive Forest	Annual Croplands = all crops but palm oil & sugar cane + other agricultural lands Permanent Croplands = oil palm & sugar cane + Plantation forests Pasture = Grasslands Extensive/Intensive Forest = 0.5*Managed forests
(Oliveira et al., 2019, 2024)	Cropland, Pasture, Managed Forest 3 intensities: Intense, Minimal, Light	Cropland = Croplands Pasture = Grassland Managed Forest = Managed Forest (using an average of the CFs for the three intensities)

In LCA, land occupation CFs, which represent the difference in ecosystem quality between current land use and a reference state, are multiplied by the land area occupied (in m².year), considering the duration of land use. In GLOBIOM, 1 year of occupation time is considered, reflecting the biodiversity impacts for the occupation in each year. This means that the biodiversity impact calculated will capture a snapshot of the biodiversity footprint of the land use in a particular year, and not include the cumulative effects of several years of land occupation on biodiversity (Bjelle et al., 2021).

The impacts of land transformation in LCA are calculated as the integral of the difference in ecosystem quality between the land use and the reference situation over the regeneration time (Koellner et al., 2013). In the same way, as in Life Cycle Inventories, the LUC flows in GLOBIOM have been separated into “from” and “to” flows (referring to the land uses before and after LUC) in order to be linked to the LC-IMPACT CFs, as well as to D2.4 CFs, which refer to the impact of transforming the reference state to the different land uses. Hence, land transformation impacts are then calculated by adding the transformation impacts from initial LU to reference (transformation impacts from reference to LU), and the transformation from final LU to reference (see Equation below and Supplementary Information from Koellner et al., 2013). Transformation impacts were allocated to the year in which the transformation happens, and only land use transformation to non-natural uses is considered.

$$Impacts_{tr} = \sum (CF_{tr,to} \cdot A_{tr,to}) - (CF_{tr,from} \cdot A_{tr,from}) \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where: $Impacts_{tr}$ is the impact related to the transformation; $CF_{tr,to}$ and $CF_{tr,from}$ are the CFs for land use transformed from natural land to the land use “to” or “from”; $A_{tr,to}$ is the area of land use transformed to Land use “to”; and $A_{tr,from}$ is the area of and use transformed from Land use “from”.

3.2.3. Interpretation of GLOBIOM results

This section highlights important considerations that need to be taken into account for the interpretation of the biodiversity loss indicators derived from GLOBIOM projections and underlying environmental flows. First, the typical environmental indicators provided by GLOBIOM (e.g., land use, input use, GHG emissions, biodiversity state) focus on environmental flows, and in some cases, endpoint CFs (e.g., biodiversity indicators) with a maximum of one pressure accounted for in the endpoint impacts (e.g., extinction risk as affected by land use). In contrast, the impacts derived from LC-IMPACT CFs only focus on endpoint impacts on ecosystem quality (terrestrial, marine and freshwater species loss), also integrating the impacts from several pressures (land stress, water stress, freshwater eutrophication, etc.). The calculated impacts are derived by linking environmental flows dynamically projected by GLOBIOM and static CFs, thereby accounting for the dynamic evolution of the amount of environmental flow per volume of product produced.

Second, the impacts for a specific time horizon t derived from LCA CFs for impact assessment explicitly integrate for each pressure the cumulative impacts over future time horizons associated with the environmental flows generated at the time horizon t , with a cut-off date of 100 years, and some explicit assumptions about the dynamics of such impacts, for example, via recovery time scales integrated in the calculation of land use transformation impacts. This deviates from indicators typically reported by GLOBIOM for the same time horizon t , usually informing on environmental flows or endpoint states at the same time horizon t . For endpoint impacts (e.g., biodiversity), the classical reported GLOBIOM state indicator, will also include consequences of environmental flows computed in previous time steps. In essence, while classical GLOBIOM indicators report environmental flows or states at a given point in time, impacts obtained from GLOBIOM coupled with LCA-derived CFs report cumulative future impacts from environmental flows at a given point in time. This means that temporal trends in both types of indicators should be displayed differently; for example, in a hypothetical scenario in which GLOBIOM projects absolute LUC that follow historical trends until 2020 and equal zero over 2030-2050, the classical GLOBIOM biodiversity indicator would show a decline until 2020 and then a flat trend from 2020 to 2050 (or some slight upward trend as pre-2020 land use changes included some land abandonment that leads to slow recovery over this area); while the LCA-based impacts from land use transformation would have positive values until 2020, a sharp drop to zero in 2030 and then remain zero. In another hypothetical scenario in which after 2020 managed land does not expand anywhere and retracts (e.g., land abandonment or restoration), the projected classical GLOBIOM biodiversity indicators will display increases over time, while the projected indicators derived from LC-IMPACT for land pressure will display sustained small positive values (or even negative values, in case the impacts from conversions from high impact managed land to low impact managed land are larger than the occupation impacts) over time. In general, a decrease (towards either smaller positive values or even negative values) in the projected LC-IMPACT-derived indicator for land pressure (or cumulated over all pressures) at a specific time horizon t (as compared to the previous time horizon) indicates that pressures at this time step t have reduced sufficiently for the related cumulated future biodiversity to be lower than that triggered by pressures in previous time step. This, however, does not guarantee that the state of biodiversity at the same time horizon t has improved as compared to the previous time step (i.e., a reversal of biodiversity loss), even though this may eventually happen at some point if the reduction in LC-IMPACT-derived indicator is sustained over time.

Finally, it must be highlighted that while the method allows the impact of several pressures on biodiversity to be captured, only those related to the land use activities covered in GLOBIOM are included. While for land use and LUC, this should provide a good approximation of total human impact (even though missing impacts such as urban area expansion are not covered in GLOBIOM), for some other pressures (for example, climate change), this will only represent a share of total human impacts.

3.2.4. Scenario analysis

To illustrate the linkage between LCA impact assessment methods and GLOBIOM, in Section 4.4, the impacts on biodiversity of agricultural and forestry activities are examined on a global scale projected by GLOBIOM combined with LCIA methods for selected Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios (SSP1-3). The SSPs are a set of explorative scenarios designed to explore future challenges to climate change impacts and mitigation and have been widely used in global change analysis (O'Neill et al., 2017, 2020). They have dedicated storylines for the main land-use sectors (Popp et al., 2017) that include contrasted trends for changes in demand, trade, technological progress affecting the productivity and input use efficiency of agricultural activities, as well as protected areas expansion and deforestation control, altogether leading to contrasted trends in land use, land use change and other environmental flows. They have been quantified with GLOBIOM (Fricko et al., 2017) and multiple other global land use models (e.g., Stehfest et al., 2019), therefore providing a well-understood scenario set to test the coupling between GLOBIOM and LCIA methods. The analysis will focus on exploring patterns in the different impact drivers (climate change, land use, water stress, and freshwater eutrophication) for terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems at global and regional scale (i.e., 59 GLOBIOM regions) as projected for the year 2020, and future trends in global scale impacts as affected by changes in production levels and input use efficiency.

Additionally, a comparative analysis will be conducted for South America and Africa, where the study will contrast environmental indicators derived from global LCA impact assessment methods, such as LC-IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020), with those obtained from D4.2 using tailored methods specific to the region (Oliveira et al., 2019, 2024). This comparison aims to highlight the potential discrepancies and the added value of using region-specific data in understanding localized environmental impacts within broader global trends.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. New set of CFs on biodiversity loss for South America and Africa

The CFs for loss of species richness for direct land occupation and land transformation based on CLEVER D2.4 for different human-modified habitats associated to the type of land use and its intensity level in South America and Africa are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The CFs show a large range of scores through the ecoregions, from $8.2 \cdot 10^{-17}$ to $14.2 \cdot 10^{-13}$ PDF·m⁻² for land occupation, and from $1.4 \cdot 10^{-13}$ to $6.2 \cdot 10^{-11}$ for land transformation. These CFs correspond to human-modified habitats for cropland, managed forest, pasture, and urban uses, mainly with a minimal intensity level that prevails in most ecoregions of both zones. Light and intense uses of cropland are also

present in various ecoregions. A marked pattern in the spatial distribution of the CFs is the high scores in the ecoregions near the edge of the respective continents.

Figure 2. Global land occupation characterisation factors for different human-modified habitats in South America and Africa at the ecoregion level based on D2.4.

When comparing this set of CFs with that of Scherer et al. (2023), the most recent available in the LCA literature, the main difference lies in the method used to estimate the biodiversity indicator applied, namely species richness, which affect directly in the regional CFs for land occupation; thus, the comparison is made for these CFs (Figure 4). Different results are obtained depending on the type of modified habitat. From the application of the Wilcoxon pairwise comparison test, it is contrasted that the CFs based on D2.4 are significantly lower in light and intense cropland, whereas for managed forest and pasture uses at minimal intensity are statistically higher.

Figure 3. Global land transformation characterisation factors for different human-modified habitats in South America and Africa at the ecoregion level based on D2.4.

Figure 4. Absolute differences, potential disappeared fraction of species (PDF) per m², between land occupation characterisation factors estimated based on the OCEUB model (Oliveira et al., 2019, 2024) and with classical approach (Scherer et al., 2023). * Scores based on the OCEUB model are significantly higher. * Scores based on the OCEUB model are significantly lower.

4.3. Biodiversity loss from Brazilian soybean exports to the EU

The implementation of the two sets of CFs presented above to assess the biodiversity loss caused by the soy supply chains gives as a first result the integrated indicators of biodiversity loss (PDF·ha⁻¹) derived from land transformation and land occupation associated with soy farming at the municipality level in Brazil. These indicators are estimated for the years of study (2004-2020); for a straightforward interpretation, those corresponding to 2020 are presented in Fig 5. In line with the above-mentioned comparison between the two sets of CFs for light and intense cropland, higher scores are obtained when using the ones from Scherer et al. (2023). The intense deforestation induced by soy crops is reflected in the greater impact scores for the municipalities located in states such as Rio Grande do Sul and Maranhão.

Figure 5. Biodiversity loss induced by land use for soy crops management practices in 2020 at the Brazilian municipality level based on the OCEUB model (Oliveira et al., 2019, 2024) and with a classical approach (Scherer et al., 2023).

The scores of the biodiversity loss indicators at the municipality level, together with the biodiversity impacts caused by the remaining links of the supply chains enabled us to estimate the biodiversity footprint of the Brazilian soy commodities marketed in the EU between 2004 and 2020. To ensure the accuracy of the estimations, as described in Section 3.1, the analysed supply chains comprise three nodes, namely the municipality producer as the supply node, the exporting port in Brazil as the intermediate node and the port of destination in the EU as the demand node. However, to facilitate the analysis of the results, they are aggregated at the state level in the origin node while the intermediate node is disregarded. Fig 6. Shows the results corresponding to the year 2020. These are estimated based on Scherer et al. (2023) and certain effects of LC-Impact, as the most conservative scenario with less uncertainty. The export of 262,438 thousand tonnes of soy-eq. in total has a median biodiversity footprint of $2.26 \cdot 10^{-2}$ PDF, ranging between $1.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$ and $3.14 \cdot 10^{-2}$ PDF (at 5% of significance) from 2004 to 2020 with a yearly average of $1.22 \cdot 10^{-3}$ PDF. Land use is identified as the most representative source of biodiversity impacts, both by land resource demand through the period and the subsequent effect of changes in C stocks. The contribution of farming, processing and transport activities is significantly lower. A downward trend in the footprint is observed throughout the analysed period, which is highly positively correlated (τ Kendall = 0.51 and ρ Spearman = 0.69) with the volume of soy traded (Figure 6). This behaviour is expected in the context of the growing scarcity

of land available for deforestation and the land demand for other types of use, understanding the influence of deforestation in the impact analysed.

As to the volume traded, soy equivalent flows arriving in the Netherlands, Spain, Germany and France and originating from Paraná, Mato Grosso, and Rio Grande do Sul are the links supply chains that contribute the most to the loss of biodiversity. It is worth noting that the soybean arriving in Spain is identified as a hotspot not only because it is the second largest soy importer, but also because a great share of the imports come from origins with a high marginal impact, namely Maranhão, Tocantins, and Amapá.

Figure 6. Biodiversity footprint of soy commodities traded from Brazil to the European Union. Estimations using LC-IMPACT endpoint CFs, except for biodiversity loss from land use impact that was estimated with Scherer et al. (2023).

4.4 Implementation in GLOBIOM

4.4.1. Simulated impacts for 2020

Figure 7 represents the absolute impacts of agricultural and forestry activities on aquatic and terrestrial biodiversity in PDF.year as well as the share of the different impact drivers in the total footprint, for 59 aggregated regions as well as globally, as calculated using LC-IMPACT CFs.

Figure 7: 2020 world and aggregated regions impacts on freshwater and terrestrial biodiversity as PDF.y and share of the different biodiversity impact drivers in the total footprint of agricultural and forestry activities. World and USA total impacts are displayed separately for ease of reading (FE: freshwater ecosystems; TE: terrestrial ecosystems)

Based on the results shown in Figure 7, the primary impact on freshwater ecosystems due to agricultural and forestry activities is water stress. However, it should also be noted that the impact of water stress might be slightly overestimated since we used water withdrawal in place of water consumption. Global freshwater eutrophication, on the other hand, is the lowest (around 2.5% of the global aquatic footprint in 2020) but might be underestimated since the CFs for freshwater eutrophication in LC-IMPACT focus exclusively on phosphorus, which is the primary limiting nutrient in freshwater ecosystems. However, the impact of excess nitrogen could also be significant (Verones et al., 2017a). Although the global impact of climate change and freshwater eutrophication on aquatic ecosystems is often relatively small in regions with a higher overall impact, these drivers dominate in specific regions (for example, China, Central

Eastern Europe, or Brazil), where they collectively account for the majority of impacts on aquatic ecosystem.

In contrast, terrestrial ecosystem impacts caused by agricultural and forestry activities are primarily driven by land stress (land use and land use change account for respectively 58% and 33% of the global terrestrial footprint in 2020), with the most significant impacts concentrated in the Southern hemisphere. Regions such as Latin America, Sub-Saharan Africa, and Southeast Asia are particularly affected by land use and land use change impacts. Some countries in Europe, ie. Denmark, Ireland, and Belgium have a higher share of climate change impacts.

Figure 8: Spatial distribution of the different biodiversity impact drivers in 2020

Figure 8 provides a more precise representation of the regional distribution of each pressure on terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity in 2020. Across all impact categories, except for water stress, South America —particularly Brazil— exhibits the highest scores. Similarly, Southern and Western Africa, India, and China also show significant impact scores across most pressures. While the spatial distribution is generally consistent across the different pressures, water stress remains a notable exception, being largely dominated by the impact of the USA. This is largely due to the high CFs for water consumption in the US within the LC-IMPACT framework, which account for the presence of numerous wetlands and a large number of vulnerable species, as discussed in Verones et al. (2017a) and Verones et al. (2017b).

4.4.2. Evolution of impact over time for future scenarios

To support the analysis of the projected impacts over time for the different scenarios (SSP1, SSP2, SSP3), Figure 9 provides an overview of the evolution of key agricultural parameters related to environmental flows per unit of product —yield, water intensity, phosphorus intensity, and GHG emissions— across ten aggregated regions as well as globally. In most regions, yields gradually increase while water and phosphorous input use intensities and GHG emission intensity decrease from 2020 onward. Under the SSP2 scenario, global GHG emission intensity is projected to decrease by 18% compared to 2020 levels, while water use intensity by 23%, and Phosphorus use intensity by 19%. Although SSP1 is generally the scenario showing the greatest improvements in efficiency and input intensity, Figure 9 shows that for phosphorus,

SSP1 sometimes has the highest intensity, even if the differences between the three scenarios are not high (globally in 2050, there is only 2% difference between SSP1-3 and SSP2). This is a result of the way the phosphorus cycle is modelled in GLOBIOM following the nutrient cycle accounting adopted by Chang et al. (2021), which should be refined to better reflect differences in the different SSPs, with explicit assumptions about agricultural input use efficiency (see Appendix A to (Popp et al., 2017)).

Figure 9: Evolution over time of yield, water intensity, Phosphorus intensity, and GHG emissions intensity for the different scenarios, and aggregated regions, as well as globally (in bold)

Figure 10 illustrates the total impact over time for the three scenarios. As already observed in Figure 7, the global total impacts on aquatic ecosystems are driven by water stress in the USA, which is particularly high. Over time the water stress impacts are increasing in the three scenarios, reaching 0.29 PDF-y in 2050, without clear differences between the three scenarios. On the other hand, climate change impact on aquatic ecosystems shows a clear decrease in SSP1 (-13%), while showing an increase in SSP2 and SSP3 (+18% and +10%).

For terrestrial ecosystems, the impacts are mainly driven by land stress, particularly due to land occupation. Although the impacts of climate change seem significantly lower than those from land stress, it is important to note that GLOBIOM only accounts for the agriculture and forestry sector, which contribute to only a small share of global GHG emissions. The difference between the three scenarios is particularly notable for land transformation; while all scenarios show a reduction in land transformation impact, SSP1 shows the most significant decrease, with a 71% reduction by 2050 compared to 2020 levels. In contrast, SSP2 and SSP3 show reductions of 47%

and 51%, respectively. This reflects the projected land use changes over time and scenarios, increasing (for SSP2 and SSP3) or slightly decreasing (for SSP1) the extent of managed land globally, in response to the increase for agricultural and forestry product demand, and despite increases in yields (Popp et al 2016). However, it is worth noting that the declining impacts do not indicate an immediate reversal of biodiversity loss, as the indicator measures potential species losses over time after the time step for which is reported, rather than reflecting the state of biodiversity at that time step.

Figure 10: Evolution of global biodiversity impacts of agricultural and forestry activities between 2010 and 2050 for SSP1, SSP2 and SSP3

Figure 11 illustrates the relationship between the percentage change in environmental flow intensity from 2000 to 2050 and the corresponding percentage change in impact in the different scenarios and for the different impact drivers.

Figure 11: Comparison between change in input intensity and change in biodiversity impacts between 2020 and 2050, globally as well as for 10 aggregated regions, and for the three scenarios.

Several key insights regarding the relationship between production, input intensity and impacts on ecosystems can be highlighted in Figure 11. First, in relative terms, the largest increases in production (size of the symbols) are directly associated with the largest increases in environmental impacts. This indicates that regions with the highest production growth, such as Sub-Saharan Africa and Southeast Asia, will also face the most significant pressure on ecosystems.

Additionally, it should be noted that trends in input use intensity can be more contrasted at the regional than at the global scale (with sometimes trends of opposite sign) and that the relationship between change in input use intensity, production and impacts can be complex at the regional scale. In general, for all pressures, there seems to be a correlation between changes in input use intensity and changes in impact, although this is not always the case. For example, a reduction of irrigation intensity of 44% in *PacificOECD* with a 61% increase in production leads to a 56% increase in impact, whereas a reduction of 35% in *FormerSovietUnion* with a 58% increase in production leads to a 2% increase in impact. The variation of impact can be related to the change in production and the change in input intensity but also to the spatially explicit nature of biodiversity and the difference in species number and endemics in the different countries (Verones et al., 2017a). This underlines the importance of using spatially-explicit CFs, such as the ones from LC-IMPACT or D2.4 from CLEVER.

4.4.3. Land use – biodiversity model comparison

For the impact on biodiversity due to land stress, the LC-IMPACT and D2.4 CFs for land occupation and transformation have been implemented in regions where both are available, and the resulting projected impacts have been compared. Similar geographical patterns can be observed from the two estimates (Figure 12), with, for example, relatively larger impacts on the coast in the Northwest of the continent (and to some extent, South-Eastern Brazil) for South America, and in Madagascar (and to some extent, Southern and Eastern Africa) for Africa. However, LC-IMPACT estimates in high-impact regions appear lower than D2.4 estimates.

Figure 12: 2020 Biodiversity impacts due to land occupation in South America and Africa as calculated with LC-IMPACT and D2.4 CFs

Figure 13 below shows the evolution of biodiversity impacts due to agricultural and forestry activities in terms of total land occupation and land transformation over time when using different estimates in South America and in Africa. The results show that land occupation follows similar trends in Africa and in South America, with a steady increase over time, and that the overall impact is slightly higher in Africa than in South America. For LUC impacts, a decrease over time is observed, similar to the global impacts previously described. However, this decline begins either in 2020 or 2030, depending on the scenario and biodiversity model used. While the trends over time of total land occupation impact in Africa between LC-IMPACT and WP2 are similar, the impacts calculated from D2.4 CFs appear higher than from LC-IMPACT. LUC impacts are notably higher also according to D2.4 CFs, except in SSP1, where both estimations are close, especially in South America.

Figure 13: Evolution of land occupation and land transformation impacts as calculated using D2.4 CFs as well as with LC-IMPACT in South America and Africa

Figure 14 displays in more detail the differences in terms of the spatial distribution of the land occupation impacts calculated based on LC-IMPACTs and based on D2.4 in both continents and for 2020. It can be noticed that in both continents, but especially in South America, *cropland* impacts appear lower when calculated with D2.4 CFs. On the other hand, impacts due to *pasture* and specially managed forest occupation show more differences. For instance, the managed forests in Eastern Brazil and around Tanzania seem to lead to significantly greater impacts when using D2.4 CFs than with LC-IMPACT. These spatial variations imply that an assessment of estimates in impacts for current and future scenarios at relatively aggregated scales hides a higher level of disagreement at more disaggregated scales. However, these disagreements likely occur in places with relatively low density of cropland, pasture and managed forest and/or places where these land uses do not change much across scenarios and time horizons.

Figure 14: Differences between the impacts on terrestrial biodiversity due to land occupation impacts as calculated when using D2.4 CFs and when using LC-IMPACT. In red are areas where impact as calculated with D2.4 CFs are higher than those with LC-IMPACT, and in blue, lower.

The differences between the two estimates might come from different sources. Firstly, the CFs based on D2.4 were calculated using a methodology, which differs from the approach used by LC-IMPACT. Like Scherer et al. (2023), Global Extinction Probabilities (Kuipers et al., 2019; Verones et al., 2022) were used for calculating Global-PDF, whereas LC-IMPACT used Vulnerability Scores (Verones et al., 2020). Similar to Scherer et al. (2023), D2.4 also implicitly includes impacts from fragmentation and distinguishes between different intensities of land use. It is worth mentioning that the fragmentation effect is based on current fragmentation patterns (embedded in CF estimates) and does not account for future changes in fragmentation. In addition, the estimations of species loss from D2.4 used to calculate the CFs, show differences compared to the ones used in LC-IMPACT: besides including additional taxonomic groups, they also used a novel approach to incorporate sampling efforts for improving accuracy. The results of this approach and the overall methodology are further described in CLEVER Deliverable 2.2, 2.3 as well as in Oliveira et al. (2019, 2024).

4.4.4. Discussion of the outputs

This section discusses the results, as well as the limitations of the study, the methodological decisions and assumptions made in integrating LC-IMPACT CFs and those derived from D2.4 into the GLOBIOM model.

The application of the LC-IMPACT CFs to the environmental flows in the output of the GLOBIOM model allowed expanding the range of biodiversity pressures related to the agricultural and forestry sectors covered. The analysis of impacts around 2020 and for future scenarios permitted the display of the resulting indicators and their projections and uncovered the relatively high level of detail achieved in terms of the link between biodiversity and human activities. This includes contrasted levels of impacts across regions (and even within countries) for each pressure and the dominance of specific pressures in total impacts at a global level but a more contrasted ranking of pressures across regions. Consistently over impacts for 2020 and future projections, land stress is the main driver of the biodiversity impact on terrestrial ecosystems and water stress is the main driver of the impact on the aquatic ecosystems. South America, and more specifically Brazil, shows the highest impacts for all the environmental pressures, except water stress, where the USA is driving the globally aggregated impacts. Another relevant level of methodological detail lies in the interplay between future changes in production, input use efficiency or GHG emission intensity, and impacts. It was observed that future changes in both production levels and input use intensity or GHG emission intensity are important to understand future impacts and that the relationship between these three factors may sometimes not be straightforward when analysed at an aggregated spatial scale, due to the high spatial heterogeneity in each of these factors: for example, sub-national patterns in changes in production, yields and fertilization or irrigation practices, as well as of the level endemism of locally present species, altogether are important determinants of impacts at aggregated scale and their link to indirect drivers such as the demand for agricultural products. This emphasizes the value of the methodological developments described in this deliverable.

When comparing the impacts of agricultural and forest activities on terrestrial biodiversity for land stress and species richness calculated with LC-IMPACT and D2.4 CFs, we found that impacts generally align between CF sources at an aggregated scale, although WP2 impacts are usually higher. However, the spatial distribution of the impacts can differ.

This deliverable also highlights several limitations that should be borne in mind when interpreting the results, which could guide future model development efforts. First, the coupling of GLOBIOM and LC-IMPACT does not account for all the relevant biodiversity impacts (such as terrestrial and freshwater ecotoxicity, marine eutrophication, and terrestrial acidification) and supply chain steps (i.e., beyond on-farm production) that could be accessed by using LC-IMPACT, therefore leads to projections of impacts clearly lower than total human impacts from all economic sectors, and underestimated for the agricultural supply chains. Future work will need to estimate additional environmental flows, such as pesticide inputs and SO_x emissions, to expand the range of impacts considered. In addition, the results described in Section 4.3 on the biodiversity footprint of other links of the Brazilian soy supply chain, should be implemented as coefficients (impacts per ton of soy) in GLOBIOM.

Besides, a finer relationship between the land use categories in LC-IMPACT and GLOBIOM is essential to better represent land use impacts. Currently, GLOBIOM's "Managed forest" is equally distributed into LC-IMPACT's "Intensive forestry" and "Extensive forestry". This categorisation lacks the nuance needed to represent the varying impacts of different land use intensities fully. This linkage will be revisited and refined following developments undertaken in the forestry sector in Task 6.2 of the CLEVER project. Similarly, to connect CFs from D2.4 with GLOBIOM, the intensities provided have been aggregated to match the existing GLOBIOM land

use categories. While this was necessary for the integration into GLOBIOM, the process involved losing some of the differentiation between land use intensities, which limits the precision in assessing the impacts of land intensification. Future improvements should focus on maintaining this intensity differentiation to better account for varying degrees of land use intensities.

CONCLUSIONS

Soybeans from Brazil are assessed as an example of one of the most internationally traded products, largely associated with LUC, deforestation and subsequent biodiversity loss in the last decades. The case study results on the biodiversity footprint of Brazilian soy supply chains highlight land stress as the primary driver of biodiversity loss, where land stress (transformation and occupation) is the leading cause. Conversely, the upstream processes involved in the supply chains cause impacts such as climate change, acidification or eutrophication, ultimately affecting ecosystem quality, although their effect is very low. Nevertheless, we consider that assessing all the drivers along supply chains is crucial to understanding this impact in an integral way, capturing the dynamics of the supply chains and increasing the accuracy of the calculations.

Applying the LC-IMPACT and D2.4 CFs to the environmental flows generated by the GLOBIOM model broadened the understanding of biodiversity pressures associated with the agriculture and forestry sectors and their long-term dynamics. The analysis identified land occupation and land use change as the primary contributors to the impact on terrestrial ecosystems, currently and in future scenarios, with SSP1 showing the largest decrease in impact, following the projected LUC. The projections also revealed significant spatial variability in impacts due to the changes in production and input intensity and the CFs themselves. However, this analysis provides only a partial picture of the impacts since it does not account for all relevant agricultural pressures (such as terrestrial and freshwater ecotoxicity, marine eutrophication, and terrestrial acidification) and supply chain steps. Further work is therefore needed to better account for land intensification as well as supply chain impacts. A critical limitation of the LCA impact assessment methods applied in this deliverable is their limited ability to reflect the potential beneficial effects on biodiversity.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

- Biodiversity loss characterisation factors for land occupation and land transformation based on estimations of species richness CLEVER D2.4
- Biodiversity loss indicators at the municipality level
- Biodiversity footprint of the supply chains of Brazilian soy arriving in the EU from 2004 to 2020 (PDF · supply chain⁻¹)

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